

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO ENGLISH TEACHING OF PRE-SCHOOL AND PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract: *The study of language is of great importance in solving many pressing practical problems beyond the independent, national interest. The theory and methodology of speech development is a science that studies the general laws of preschool education, the nature and problems of educating preschool children in accordance with a single social purpose in a particular society. The theory and methodology of speech development is a science that is part of the social sciences and studies the problems of educating and training preschool and primary school children in physical and mental development.*

Keywords: *innovation, approach, teaching, learning, foreign language, preschool, primary school.*

INTRODUCTION

The theory, which emerges as the initial stage of organizing knowledge, is formed in language, which gives language a special place in the process of learning and thus opens new scientific horizons for the science of language. The formation of the individual is carried out through the acquisition of social and structural experience created by human society, education. This occurs in a variety of activities. The choice of content that children should acquire, the guidance of its acquisition is carried out by adults in the educational process. The content, means, methods of upbringing and education, the process of development of the child are explained by their age. In particular, when working with young children, it is taken into account that they are not completely adapted to independent living. Another characteristic of man, his own human need, is the need to communicate with other people, the "need for emotional communication." It was precisely because of this need that language first emerged. The need for communication always leads to language acquisition.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

It turns out that a high level of speech development in preschool adults can be achieved at the expense of:

- awareness of the literary norms and rules of the language;
- be able to freely express their views;
- ability to communicate, interact with adults and peers;

- be able to listen to the interlocutor, ask (ask questions correctly), answer, object, and, if necessary, explain, explain.

Special attention should be paid to the development of speech-dialogic and monologue speech in the development of speech in preschool adults. The theory and methodology of speech development is a science that studies the general laws of preschool education, the nature and problems of raising and educating preschool children in a particular society in accordance with a single social goal. The theory and methodology of speech development is a science that is part of the social sciences and studies the problems of educating and training preschool children in physical and mental development.

The main content of the methodology of speech development is the organization of organizational pedagogical and methodological work on the development of oral speech in children, its children's speech. Improving the level of speech correction in the development of speech in preschool adults is one of the main tasks before the methodologists of the preschool education system. With this in mind, it is advisable to start the research on the problem of speech development of older children of preschool age in the study of the environment by identifying the factors that ensure speech development.

The student's personal creative experience and creative reading method will greatly help to fulfill these conditions. Reading a work of art is qualitatively different from reading a work of science or journalism. Creative reading requires special attention to words, sentences, and weight.

Creative reading method. The creative reading method is unique to literature. Because an important part of the science of literature is the art of words. The main feature of a creative reading method is the development of artistic taste, artistic experience and ability in the student through the work of art. As the methodologist M.

Mirkasimova points out: "Literary analysis begins with the expressive reading of a poem or prose; During reading, the way of thinking created by the artist is understood, mastered, discussed, and the poetic scene or situation created in the reader's eyes is perceived and felt through both external and internal actions and feelings.

Artistic perception Aesthetic enjoyment is the first and most important step in understanding literature on a scientific basis. Because through artistic perception and aesthetic pleasure, the images and language of the work are mastered. Research (heuristic) method. Heuristics (Greek heurisko - search, find, discover) develops within the boundaries of psychology, cybernetics, information theory as a field of science that studies human creative activity, as well as the methods used to create new discoveries. The application of heuristic teaching methods requires the teacher to search for new knowledge by various means. The teacher shares some of the knowledge with the students, and the rest is acquired by the students based on finding

answers to the questions in the process of solving the cognitive tasks, they acquire the knowledge independently. It is important for the teacher to divide the problem into several points of view, and for students to follow the sequence in their implementation. Therefore, this method is also called the partial search method.

Research method. The third stage in the study of literature is the development of creative thinking, the discovery and analysis of the essence of the work of art through independent work aimed at acquiring research activities. The study of a work of art in this order gives rise to a method of research. The purpose of the research method is to shed more light on the specifics of literature, to prepare students for independent analysis of literary works, to develop their skills in assessing the ideological and artistic significance of the work, to improve their art.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Appropriate methods are used in all areas of human activity. Given the general nature of these methods, they can be called a set of operations and ways of practical or theoretical assimilation of an entity. This article discusses the aspects of the concept of method related to the educational process. Accordingly, we will consider the methods and techniques associated with teaching methods. The most effective type of teaching method is, of course, interactive methods. An interactive method is a method that activates learners and encourages them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the learning process. These methods encourage the learner to be actively involved. Here are some interactive methods.

Lingvopoetist method. This method is one of the most effective interactive methods that help to strengthen students' memory, the formation of personal thinking, independent thinking. The method is carried out in 2 stages. In the first stage, students are read an excerpt from a particular work of art or poem (texts must be covered in a literature class), but the title and author are not given. Then, in the second stage, in the form of a mental attack, "If you were to say that, how would you express it?" the question is asked and the text is asked to be edited in accordance with the idea. Each student completes a written assignment and reads it aloud. It is especially useful if prose and poetic texts in the context of Motherland, Parents, and Nature are chosen as examples and used in repetition lessons. At the end of the lesson, the sentences in the texts are analyzed. The best texts will be identified and the author will be awarded the title of "Lingvopoetist".

CONCLUSION

In short, every educator must organize the process of education and upbringing creatively, based on their abilities and professional skills. The use of innovative technologies in the classroom requires students to develop independent, free and creative thinking skills, to be active, to take creative approaches to understanding the information being learned.

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